

Propagation models in single/multi-radio scenarios: overview and influence analysis

J.M. García*[‡], F.J. Estévez*[‡], G. Rebel*[‡], J.M. Castillo-Secilla[‡], J. González[‡] and P. Glösekötter*

*Lab. for Semiconductor Devices & Bussystems

University of Applied Sciences of Münster, Münster, Germany

Email: jose_m_garcia@fh-muenster.de

[†]Dept. of Computer Technology and Computation

University of Alicante, Alicante, Spain

[‡]Dept. of Computer Architecture and Technology

University of Granada, Granada, Spain

Email: jesugonzalez@ugr.es

Abstract—The evolution in low power communications and low cost electronics is pushing up the deployment of more and more devices, which traduces in an overcrowded radio electrical environment. This overcrowd requires new mechanisms to mitigate it, and therefore, Cognitive Radio and Multi Radio techniques become relevant. These techniques are gaining the attention of the research community, becoming a trendy research theme. Due to the difficulty for deploying large networks with research purposes, simulators arises as an useful alternative. Simulators are a research field itself, being based on different components, from where propagation models is one of the principals, allowing the simulation of different environment conditions. This work presents a deep analysis of the different wireless propagation models in a well-known simulator, focusing on the packet delivery ratio, error rate and energy consumption. The different models are compared under different conditions, varying the node density and sending frequency of each scenario.

Index Terms—propagation models, multi radio, WSN, AODV

I. INTRODUCTION

The evolution in low power communications and low cost hardware is pushing up the society into a world where everything is interconnected. Crowd of connected devices is based on Wireless Sensor Networks (WSN), [1] due to the worldwide legal limitations tend to use the 2.4GHz Industrial, Scientific and Medical (ISM) band. Nowadays researchers are studying how to mitigate the impact of a huge amount of devices working in the same frequency. Depending on the frequency, each standard defines a number of channels, which use different management techniques. This work focuses on the analysis of low-power and low-rate wireless connectivity using the IEEE 802.15.4-standard, which defines up to 15 channels in the 2.4GHz ISM-band.

Different applications are increasing the number of devices that coexist in the same ISM-bands and channels, which derive in overcrowded channels with a high collision-rate. The increment in the number of collisions and the downturn in the throughput lead to developing new techniques that improve the coexistence such as software defined radios or cognitive radio.

The analysis of these problems is usually difficult, as long as involve hundred or thousand devices, thus the research community turns to simulation environments, which give the opportunity to study those behaviours in detail. This peak in simulation use leads us to another question, are the wireless propagation models in the simulators reliable enough? How do they influence a study? These open questions are studied in the present article, analyzing the impact of different wireless propagation models to different scenarios based on single-/multi-radio and node density.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II provides an overview of different wireless propagation models available for simulation, as long as a short literature review. Section III presents the system design, which is mainly focused on minimizing the collisions in order to improve the throughput of the networks. Section IV presents a deep analysis in terms of Packet Delivery Ratio (PDR), Error Rate (ER) and energy consumption for the propagation models analyzed. Finally, in Section V the results are discussed and the most relevant conclusions of this paper are presented.

II. STATE OF ART

The study of wireless propagation models in simulation environment is not under the focus of the research community, regardless its importance. Lots of studies such as [2], [3], [4], [5] or [6] are based on simulation results to justify their innovation, but not as many studies analyze the impact of wireless propagation models in the results obtained. Some studies such as [7], discuss about the improvement in the propagation characteristics through the use of cognitive radio techniques. Nevertheless, and in spite of the fact that this work considers the propagation models characteristics, it does not evaluate different propagation models, remaining open the question about the impact of the wireless propagation models on the results.

Grudén et al. [8] have analyzed the radio environment in a close space, such as a jet engine, carrying out empirical tests. From those tests they simply consider the environmental factor inside the jet engine, discarding the comparison with

different wireless propagation models. In the same way goes the work of Patri et al. [9]. Their work analyses the radio frequency propagation in an underground coal mine. They focus on some physical parameters such as path loss, node distance and packet error rate (PER), but they do not consider the impact of using other propagation models.

Another interesting work has been developed by He et al. [10]. They discussed different propagation models and proposed a new one based on 3D radio propagation environments for indoor ZigBee WSNs. This new wireless propagation model considers the nearby obstacles, but it is mainly focused on indoor environments, discarding outdoor scenarios. The authors carry out a comparison between the simulated propagation model and a real use case where they validate their model, but do not consider the analysis of different propagation models for simulation purposes.

However, different propagation models already exist in the network simulators. For example, OMNeT++, a well known network simulator includes both idealistic and realistic models [11], allowing the researchers to test the behaviour under several propagation circumstances.

Propagation models can be classified into two groups: deterministic and probabilistic models. Deterministic models are conceived to represent the radio behaviour without taking into account the environment. They adjust the range of the antenna depending on the radio parameters, such as the transmitter power, the antenna gain and so on. Probabilistic models take a different approach simulating environment effects like reflections with external objects or interactions between radios. Some of the most representative models are described below.

A. Free Space Model

This model is a deterministic model that calculates the signal attenuation over a given distance d . Eq. 1 defines how the signal decreases, depending on the radio parameters:

$$Pr_{det}(d) = \frac{P_t G_t G_r \lambda}{(4\pi)^2 d^2 L} \quad (1)$$

where P_t represents the transmission power, G_t and G_r the gain of the transmitter and receiver antenna, λ is the wavelength and L is the loss factor. The main disadvantage of the model is its deterministic behaviour. Physical effects like fast fading, reflection or scattering are not taken into account, so it is an ideal approach.

B. Two Ray Ground Model

This is another deterministic model, which determines the signal attenuation similarly to the *Free Space* model, but considering the reflection on the ground too. Eq. 2 defines the path loss:

$$Pr_{det}(d) = \frac{P_t G_t G_r h_t^2 h_r^2}{d^4} \quad (2)$$

where h_t and h_r represent the height of the transceiver's and receiver's antenna. Despite it is less idealistic than the *Free Space*, it is not a realistic model.

C. Log Normal Shadowing Model

This is a probabilistic model which employs a normal distribution to hand out reception power in the logarithmic domain. The σ of the normal distribution can be modified, obtaining the following expression for the log-normal distribution:

$$Pr_{LogNormal}(d; \sigma^2) \sim LN(Pr_{det}(d), \sigma^2) \quad (3)$$

D. Rayleigh Model

This is also a probabilistic model which provides intensive variation of the reception power for non-line-of-sight communications. It hands out the reception power using a Rayleigh distribution. The deterministic model serves as a base to calculate the average power for the distribution.

$$Pr_{Rayleigh}(d) \sim Rayleigh(Pr_{det}(d)) \quad (4)$$

E. Rice Model

This model takes the Rayleigh one as a base and includes the positive effects of a line-of-sight path to calculate the reception power, as is shown in Eq 5:

$$Pr_{Rice}(d, k) \sim Rayleigh(Pr_{det}(d), k) \quad (5)$$

where k is the parameter which involves the associated effects of a line-of-sight path. It offers a more realistic alternative than the *Rayleigh* model.

F. Nakagami Model

This probabilistic model takes into account the fading effects on the signal to disseminate the reception power using a gamma distribution, as is shown in Eq. 6:

$$Pr_{Nakagami}(d; m) \sim Gamma(m, \frac{Pr_{det}(d)}{m}) \quad (6)$$

where the m parameter defines the fading effects. It has proved itself well suited to reflect some realistic conditions [12].

III. METHODOLOGY

This work has been developed over the standard IEEE 802.15.4, because it is commonly used as a base for the majority of WSN protocols.

The simulation software selected to carry out this comparative study was OMNeT++, due to its capacity to simulate a wide range of standard and non-standards protocols. However, the software itself does not provide any protocol. It is necessary to download model frameworks developed as independent projects. For WSN, the framework used was *INETMANET*, a branch of the *INET* framework that contains the standard model library of OMNeT++, adding several additional features mainly for mobile ad-hoc networks and Wireless Personal Area Networks (WPANs).

The different elements from a network are implemented in OMNeT++ through modules. These modules are single objects that contain both, the functionality of a full-functional network stack, covering from physical-layer to application layer and the battery, wireless channel control, terminal interface, etc. Therefore, the channel control module is responsible for

Parameter	Value
Effective Range (m)	65
Carrier Frequency (GHz)	2.4
Carrier sense sensitivity (dBm)	-85
Transmit power (mW)	0.2
MAC queue length	50
MAC Ack	Disabled
Routing Protocol	AODV
Message Length (Bytes)	70
Channel number Single-Radio	0
Channel number Multi-Radio	0 / 5
Path Loss Alpha	2
SNR threshold (dB)	4
Transceiver High (m)	1
Receiver High (m)	1
Sigma	1
Nakagami m	1
K (dB)	8

TABLE I: Main fixed simulation parameters

handling the information about radio interfaces of nodes at transmissions. For this reason, the main objective was to evaluate the network behaviour depending on the propagation model configured on the channel control module.

As a starting point, it was decided to compare the performance over a single-radio model and the multi-radio model, presented in [13], using a representative example in OMNeT++. Since the multi-radio model developed in the previous work was implemented using AODV, this study uses the same basic scheme allowing us to compare the results between the two radio models.

The AODV example selected exists for OMNeT++ in the framework *INETMANET*. It is called *csma802154*, and it is included in the *wpan* examples folder. Nodes present in this network example contain different modules like the referent to the User Datagram Protocol (UDP), the Transmission Control Protocol (TCP) or the Internet Protocol (IP), a routing module for mobile ad-hoc networks (MANETs) and a battery module. Furthermore, the module of the Network Interface Card (NIC), corresponding to an IEEE 802.15.4 standard interface is also present.

Modifying the propagation model of this example is a trivial task, because the module contains a parameter with several propagation models, including the *Free Space* model, the *Two Ray Ground* model, the *Rice* model, the *Rayleigh* model, the *Nakagami* model and the *Log-normal Shadowing* model.

IV. EXPERIMENT AND RESULTS

Simulations have been carried out using a static scenario. The nodes are placed applying a random spatial distribution in a two-dimensional square area. In the interest of making these experiments reproducible, we present the main parameters of physical, link and network layer in Table I.

After a testing period checking the correct behaviour of the simulation, the time was limited to 3600 seconds, due to memory restrictions.

The test context is focused on the comparative between the 6 propagation models described in Section II. In order

Parameter	Value
Number of sending nodes	5 / 9
Number of multiple destination nodes	3
Node degree	5 / 15
Time between messages	1 / 30

TABLE II: Main variable simulation parameters

to try out these models, several scenarios have been carried out. The main goal was to observe the behaviour under diverse conditions, showing an overall conception about their performance. The variable parameters modified during the simulation runs are shown in Table II.

The comparison is based on two different interval times, 1 and 30 seconds. are not arbitrary values but they have proved themselves as uncorrelated frequencies in the Kruskal-Wallis test. For these sending frequencies, two different network scenarios are tested, small scenarios and large scenarios. The network size is represented through the node density (or node degree, ND), where a large scenario corresponds to ND5 and a small scenario corresponds to ND15. Both cases are compared using a low-traffic scenario, which involves up to 15 active nodes, sending and/or receiving data to/from the network. In addition, a high-traffic scenario has also been tested for the ND15, involving up to 36 nodes, sending and/or receiving data to/from the network.

To accomplish a fair comparative between models, three primary aspects of the network performance have been analysed: packet delivery ratio (PDR), error rate (CR) and energy consumption. The name of the propagation models has been abbreviated in the graphics. The abbreviations *FS*, *TR*, *RI*, *NA*, *RA* and *LN* correspond to *Free Space*, *Two Ray*, *Rice*, *Nakagami*, *Rayleigh* and *Log Normal*, respectively.

A. Packet Delivery Rate Analysis

The PDR represents the number of messages successfully sent. This parameter gives a precise overview of the propagation model details among different scenarios with different density, sending frequency and traffic conditions.

1) *Low-Traffic Scenario*: Node density 5 and 15 were analysed for a sending frequency of 1 and 30 seconds. Results shown in Fig. 1 – 4 offer interesting details about the network performance when different models are used. Generally, deterministic models present the best delivery ratio as is expected since they are conceived to represent an idealistic transmission. On the contrary, *Nakagami* and *Rayleigh* show very poor ratios, far away of deterministic results. Their means and medians are the worst among the probabilistic models. On the other hand, *Log-Normal* model seems to be the statistic model, obtaining the best ratio results. In addition, it shows close means and medians to deterministic models in some scenarios, even improving the *Log Normal* performance under density 15 and a 1 second for the sending frequency. Multi-radio examples shows the same trend than single-radio, presenting only better delivery ratios with deterministic models.

Fig. 1: PDR in low-traffic scenarios under density 5 and 1s sending frequency.

Fig. 3: PDR in low-traffic scenarios under density 15 and 1s sending frequency.

Fig. 2: PDR in low-traffic scenarios under density 5 and 30s sending frequency.

Fig. 4: PDR in low-traffic scenarios under density 15 and 30s sending frequency.

2) *High-Traffic Scenario*: In order to test the behaviour on a high traffic network, simulations were run under density 15, increasing the number of senders up to 9 nodes. Figures 5-6 show the results for these scenarios. The observed trend is similar to low-traffic. *Nakagami* and *Rayleigh* present the worst results and *Log-Normal* stands out among the probabilistic models. When probabilistic models are used, the multi-radio modules does not offer a behaviour improvement.

B. Error Rate Analysis

The collision rate or error rate indicates the amount of collisions per message sent. Lower values are associated to fewer collisions, therefore the network performance is worst for high values of this rate. Scenarios were explained in

Sections IV-A.

1) *Low-Traffic Scenario*: Node density 5 and 15 were analysed for a sending frequency of 1 and 30 seconds. Results shown in Fig. 7 – 10 does not show an overall trend. The different propagation models offer different behaviours across the scenarios. However, for most of the cases, *Two Ray* achieves the lowest error rate. Regarding on the single-radio or multi-radio performance, the error rate is fewer for the 1 second scenarios when a multi-radio device is employed. The behaviour for 30 seconds shows similar results.

2) *High-Traffic Scenario*: The high-traffic scenario included simulations under node density 15. Figures 11-12 show the results for these scenarios. The observed performance is dissimilar than low-traffic. It seems to exist a certain trend for

Fig. 5: PDR in high-traffic scenarios under density 15 and 1s sending frequency.

Fig. 7: ER in low-traffic scenarios under density 5 and 1s sending frequency.

Fig. 6: PDR in high-traffic scenarios under density 15 and 30s sending frequency.

Fig. 8: ER in low-traffic scenarios under density 5 and 30s sending frequency.

the different cases. Despite of the fact that *Two Ray* shows the lowest error rate, *Log-Normal* offers the worst behaviour in all scenarios. *Nakagami* and *Rayleigh* also present a similar behaviour along the different cases. Regarding on the radio module, the error decreases when multi-radio is used. The improvement is more significant in 1 second scenario.

Rayleigh and *Rice* median are similar but *Rayleigh* mean is considerably fewer. *Log Normal* model achieves the worst results.

C. Energy Consumption Analysis

The following figures show the consumed energy during the simulations under the same scenarios explained in Sections IV-A and IV-B.

1) *Low-Traffic Scenario*: Figures 13 – 16 show the results for node densities 5, 15 and 1, 15 seconds for sending frequency. Both radio modules were analysed, offering diverse results. *Free Space* and *Two Ray* results shows the higher consumption under node density 5. On the other hand, *Nakagami* and *Rayleigh* offer the lowest consumption among the models. As was expected, multi-radio module presents a higher consumption than the single-radio.

Under scenarios with 15 density, the trend is not so clear. Single-radio scenarios with a sending frequency of 1 second keeps the ND5 behaviour whereas the other scenarios present a completely different performance. It cannot be obtained an overall performance among the models.

Fig. 9: ER in low-traffic scenarios under density 15 and 1s sending frequency.

Fig. 11: ER in high-traffic scenarios under density 15 and 1s sending frequency.

Fig. 10: ER in low-traffic scenarios under density 15 and 30s sending frequency.

Fig. 12: ER in high-traffic scenarios under density 15 and 30s sending frequency.

2) *High-Traffic Scenario*: Scenarios under node density 15 were tested. Figures 21 – 24 show the results for these cases. As occurred in low traffic ND5 scenarios, *Nakagami* and *Rayleigh* offer the best consumption whereas *Log Normal* and *Free Space* show the worst consumption. Regarding the multi-radio behaviour, it increases the consumption of the single-radio example.

V. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This paper has carried out an analysis of the influence of propagation models in WSN. The simulations also have obtained information about their impact when a multi-radio model is used, instead a common single-radio model. Due to the amount of data provided in Section IV, we discuss the

results separately.

A. Packet Delivery Rate Discussion

Several conclusions can be obtained from Fig 1–6. Deterministic models (*Free Space* and *Two Ray*) present the best PDR in all scenarios. They barely include environmental effects on the propagation therefore it was the expected behaviour. There is also a trend for the probabilistic models. *Log Normal* stands out, showing results near deterministic models. *Rayleigh*, *Rice* and *Nakagami* models present really low rates. The reason of this behaviour could reside on the node's ability to create the routes. Since AODV needs to send messages to establish the path for packets, low delivery rates for that kind of message could prevent some routes formation. Without the

Fig. 13: Energy Consumption in low-traffic single-radio scenarios under density 5 and 1s sending frequency.

Fig. 15: Energy Consumption in low-traffic single-radio scenarios under density 5 and 30s sending frequency.

Fig. 14: Energy Consumption in low-traffic multi-radio scenarios under density 5 and 1s sending frequency.

Fig. 16: Energy Consumption in low-traffic multi-radio scenarios under density 5 and 30s sending frequency.

proper routes, PDR will decrease dramatically.

Analysing the overall performance of the network, multi-radio shows better results for a sending frequency of 1 in ND15 examples. Those scenarios present a higher traffic load, therefore, obtaining a better result using a second radio working was the expected result. When time frequency is increased to 30 seconds, single-radio nodes have enough time to handle the messages and multi-radio does not improve its behaviour. The PDR's increment for 30 seconds scenarios respecting to 1 second scenarios also supports this fact. For lower density scenarios, there are not remarkable improvements or even a downturn in terms of performance.

B. Error Rate Discussion

Figures 7–12 show the error rate results. Due to the performance differences between low and high density scenarios, a separately discussion is carried out. Low density scenarios do not present a trend among the models. There is not a conclusion which could be obtained from the results respecting to the propagation models.

Regarding on the overall behaviour, multi-radio scenarios present less collision rate than single radio's. The traffic load scenario, due to the high frequency, explains the best result achieved. On the other hand, the improvement on the network performance when the sending frequency is increased to 30 seconds, can also be observed through the lower error rates for those scenarios.

Fig. 17: Energy Consumption in low-traffic single-radio scenarios under density 15 and 1s sending frequency.

Fig. 19: Energy Consumption in low-traffic single-radio scenarios under density 15 and 30s sending frequency.

Fig. 18: Energy Consumption in low-traffic multi-radio scenarios under density 15 and 1s sending frequency.

Fig. 20: Energy Consumption in low-traffic multi-radio scenarios under density 15 and 30s sending frequency.

High density cases show a trend over the different scenarios. *Two Ray* model always shows the lowest error rate. In addition, *Free Space* model also seems to be the second best in most of the cases. Therefore, we could affirm that deterministic models present a better behaviour according to the error rate. For high traffic scenarios, multi-radio model achieves a lower error rate as was expected due to the traffic load. However, difference between both radio models becomes smaller for a sending frequency of 30 seconds.

Keeping in mind the PDR results, it does not seem to be a relation between low PDR values and abnormally high error rates. The possible cause resides on the node's ability to form the routes. If they cannot, collisions related to the application messages would not present high values whereas the packet

delivery ratio will decrease significantly.

C. Energy Consumption Discussion

Battery consumption results are shown in figures 13 – 24. It does not seem to exist an overall behaviour. For most of the single-radio scenarios, deterministic models present the higher consumption, but not for all cases. In a similar way the best consumption, associated to *Nakagami* and *Rayleigh* models. The lack of a trend prevents to determine a conclusion about the influence of radio models.

Comparing individually single-radio and multi-radio results, it can be observed a higher consumption on the multi-radio scenarios. It was the expected behaviour, due to the presence of an additional radio. However, the multi-radio consumption

Fig. 21: Energy Consumption in high-traffic single-radio scenarios under density 15 and 1s sending frequency.

Fig. 23: Energy Consumption in high-traffic single-radio scenarios under density 15 and 30s sending frequency.

Fig. 22: Energy Consumption in high-traffic multi-radio scenarios under density 15 and 1s sending frequency.

Fig. 24: Energy Consumption in high-traffic multi-radio scenarios under density 15 and 30s sending frequency.

do not duplicate single-radio consumption at any case.

D. Overall conclusion

General performance of deterministic and probabilistic models is remarkably different. Deterministic models offer a significantly better behaviour at any condition. Therefore, researchers should take into account not only idealistic environments but also realistic ones. Employing both deterministic and probabilistic models will lead to better approximations to the real performance of a WSN. Due to the dissimilar results, providing detailed information about the used model should be also a primary aspect of a research, in order to allow the replication of the experiments.

When a deterministic propagation is used, the multi-radio

model presents better results for high traffic and high node density as was presented in our previous work [13].

However, if a probabilistic propagation is used, the performance of multi-radio model is always worse than the single radio. The main reason of this behaviour could be the interactions between radios in multi-radio models.

VI. FUTURE WORK

A future work should go deeply into the misbehaviour regarding the interactions between radios. The main reason of the problem needs to be found in order to plan an achievable solution. Other research line will be analysing the behaviour under a different routing algorithm or protocol. Using a specific wireless algorithm, focused on the managing of a

multi-radio model. A multi-radio oriented policy could serve to reach or improve the single-radio behaviour for all the scenarios.

REFERENCES

- [1] D. Rudinska J. Stankunas and E. Lasauskas. Experimental Research of Wireless Sensor Network Application in Aviation. *Elektronika ir Elektrotechnika*, 111(5), 2011.
- [2] Kermajani H. and Gómez C. On the network convergence process in rpl over ieee 802.15.4 multihop networks: Improvement and trade-offs. *Sensors*, 14:11993–12022, 2014.
- [3] Chatzivasileiadis S.; Bonvini M.; Matanza J.; Zin R.X.; Noudui T.S.; Kara E.C.; Parmar R.; Lorenzetti D.; Wetter M. and Kiliccote S. Cyber-physical modeling of distributed resources for distribution system operations. In *Proceedings of the IEEE*, pages 789–806. Piscataway, NJ, USA, 2016. IEEE.
- [4] Lall S.; Maharaj B.T.J. and Van Vuuren P.A.J. Null-frequency jamming of a proactive routing protocol in wireless mesh networks. *Journal of Network and Computer Applications*, 61:133–141, 2016.
- [5] Anchora L.; Capone A.; Mainetti L.; Mighali V. and Patrono L. As2-mac: An energy-efficient mac protocol for wireless sensor networks. *Ad Hoc Sensor Wireless Networks*, 31:199–226, 2016.
- [6] Bhor D.; Angappan K. and Sivalingam K.M. Network and power-grid co-simulation framework for smart grid wide-area monitoring networks. *Journal of Network and Computer Applications*, 59:274–284, 2016.
- [7] M. Abbaspour R. Tizvar and M. Dehghani. CR-CEA: A collision-and energy-aware routing method for cognitive radio wireless sensor networks. *Wireless Networks*, (5):2037–52, May 2014.
- [8] M. Jobs M. Grudén and A. Ryydberg. Empirical Tests of Wireless Sensor Network in Jet Engine Including Characterization of Radio Wave Propagation and Fading. *IEEE Antennas and Wireless Propagation Letters*, 13:762–65, 2014.
- [9] D.S. Nimaje A. Patri and R. Odisha. Radio Frequency Propagation Model and Fading of Wireless Signal at 2.4GHz in Underground Coal Mine. *Journal South African Institute of Mining and Metallurgy*, 115:629–36, August 2015.
- [10] G. Liang J. Portilla D. He, G. Mujica and T. Riesgo. Radio propagation modeling and real test of ZigBee based indoor wireless sensor networks. *Journal of Systems Architecture*, 60:711–25, 2014.
- [11] O. Grunte H. Hartenstein A. Kuntz, F. Schmidt-Eisenlohr and M. Zitterbart. Introducing Probabilistic Radio Propagation Models in OMNeT++ Mobility Framework and Cross Validation Check with NS-2. In *SimuTools '08 Proceedings of the 1st international conference on Simulation tools and techniques for communications, networks and systems workshops*, number 72, Brussels, Belgium, 2008.
- [12] Vikas Taliwal, Daniel Jiang, Heiko Mangold, Chi Chen, and Raja Sengupta. Empirical determination of channel characteristics for dsrc vehicle-to-vehicle communication. In *Proceedings of the 1st ACM International Workshop on Vehicular Ad Hoc Networks, VANET '04*, pages 88–88, New York, NY, USA, 2004. ACM.
- [13] J.M. Castillo-Secilla J. González F. Estevez, J.M. García and P. Gloeskoetter. Enabling validation of IEEE 802.15.4 performance through a new dual-radio OMNeT++ model. *Elektronika ir Elektrotechnika*, 2016.